

Synthesis of ruthenium(III) complexes with benzimidazole derivatives

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Complexes of ruthenium with biologically important benzimidazole derivatives, viz. 2-(2'-hydroxyphenyl)benzimidazole (HOPBI), 2-(2'-mercaptophenyl)benzimidazole (HSPBI), 2-(2'-hydroxynaphthyl)benzimidazole (HONBI) have been synthesized and characterized.

Ruthenium complexes have been the subject of interest due to the fact that they play vital roles in industrial endeavors as well as biological organisms¹. Complexes of ruthenium with biologically important pyridyl and polypyridyl ligands have been investigated by several researchers because of their key role in photoluminescence, photochemistry and photophysical processes². In view of these studies, the coordination compounds of imidazoles and benzimidazoles with iron and ruthenium metal ions have been investigated³.

The present communication describes the synthesis and characterization of the complexes of ruthenium with 2-substituted-benzimidazoles.

Results and discussion

The complexes (Table 1) were coloured solids and soluble in DMSO and DMF. The low values of molar conductance (10–30 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) revealed their non-electrolytic nature. IR spectra of the ligands show strong ab-

2600 cm^{-1} (thiophenolic) were absent, indicating thereby the deprotonation and coordination of metal through this group. It is further supported by the appearance of new bands at 370–375 (Ru–O) and 330–340 cm^{-1} (Ru–S)⁵. The shifting in C–O/C–S stretching vibrations towards lower frequency (10–15 cm^{-1}) indicates the formation of C–O–M/C–S–M type of bonding in complexes. The band at 1620 cm^{-1} (C=N) in ligand shifted to lower frequency region (10–15 cm^{-1}) in the complexes indicating the coordination of tertiary nitrogen atom of the imidazolyl ring with the metal atom. This observation gets further support by the appearance of band at 340–345 cm^{-1} (Ru–N)⁶.

In the ¹H NMR of the ligands the aromatic protons appeared as a multiplet in the region of δ 6.9–7.9 ppm. The resonance signal at δ 8.5 (NH) is quite broad and not clear. However, the downfield shift is explained in view of extensive hydrogen bonding⁷. The signal around δ 10.1–10.2 ppm is due to phenolic proton. The attachment of phenolic moiety to the benzimidazole ring at 2-position and the effect of hydrogen bonding results in the formation of chelate ring with tertiary nitrogen and imino group of the benzimidazole. Therefore, the signal due to –OH proton is shifted downfield⁸. In the ¹H NMR spectra of complexes the phenyl protons are observed in the region δ 7.2–8.0 ppm. The broad signal due to NH proton of imidazolyl ring remained unperturbed and observed almost at the same position in the spectra of complexes indicating thereby the non-deprotonation and non-participation of this group on complexation. The –OH proton signal of the ligand disappeared completely in the spectra of the complexes, confirming the deprotonation of the OH group and coordination of phenolic oxygen to metal atom. Similarly, the proton signal of the ligand at δ 3.8 (SH) also disappeared in the spectra of the metal complex, suggesting the deprotonation of the SH group and coordination of thiophenolic sulfur to the metal atom. The magnetic moment values for

Table 1. Analytical and physical data

Compd. and Ligand	Colour	Decomp. temp.(°C)	Metal % : Found (Calcd.)
HOPBI (C ₁₃ H ₁₀ N ₂ O)	White	242	–
HSPBI (C ₁₃ H ₁₀ N ₂ S)	Yellow	202	–
HONBI (C ₁₇ H ₁₂ N ₂ S)	Violet	130	–
Ru(OPBI) ₃	Brown	286	13.62 (13.87)
Ru(SPBI) ₃	Black	290	12.81 (13.01)
Ru(ONBI) ₃	Brown	256	11.33 (11.50)

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analysis.

sorption bands at 1620–1630 (>C=N– of imidazolyl ring), 1590–1595 (conjugation of –C=C– with >C=N), 1460 (–C–C– stretching vibration of phenyl ring), 1410 cm^{-1} (–NH bending) etc. which appeared to be more or less same as reported in literature⁴. In the complexes the characteristic IR ligand bands at 3350–3450 (phenolic) and 2560–

the complexes (1.93–2.16 B.M.) corresponding to the presence of the one unpaired electron, indicate their paramagnetic nature. The electronic spectra of these complexes showed bands at 363, 365 and 362 nm. The ligand field strength in the complexes are of same magnitude ($10 Dq = 27000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and on the basis of $10 Dq$ values, the absorption maxima in the electronic spectra of these derivatives may be assigned to ${}^2T_{2g} - {}^2A_{2g}$ transition in the Ru^{III} ion.

Thus on the basis of above spectral studies and analytical data, a distorted octahedral structure have been proposed for these complexes.

Experimental

M.p. were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer, electronic spectra (CHCl_3) on a Pye-Unicam Sp-8-100 spectrophotometer and ${}^1\text{H}$ NMR spectra ($\text{DMSO}-d_6$) on a JEOL FX 90 Q spectrometer (90 MHz) using TMS as an internal reference. Magnetic susceptibility at room temperature was measured on a Guoy's balance using $[\text{HgCo}(\text{SCN})_4]$ as calibrant. The purity of all the compounds was checked by TLC. Ruthenium contents in the complexes were analysed by thermal decomposition ($500\text{--}600^\circ$) of the

complexes to the oxides⁹. The ligands were prepared by the reported method¹⁰. A suspension of $\text{RuCl}_3(x)$ in ethanol was refluxed until dissolution completed (1.5 h). To the resulting solution, ligand in ethanol (3x) was added. The mixture was refluxed for 4 h, during which colour changed from light brown to dark brown. The brown solution was filtered, evaporated under reduced pressure (1 mm) and dried over fused CaCl_2 to get the complexes, yield (75–78%).

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